

DIETARY SUPPLEMENTATION WITH NATURAL IMMUNOMODULATORS AND SOWS FERTILITY

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SUMMARY: The influence of feeding the sows by diets supplemented with natural immunomodulators on fertility parameters, were investigated on one large pig farm in AP Vojvodina (Serbia). The diets of pregnant, lactating and weaned sows (in the period weaning-to-fertile estrus) were supplemented with preparations containing premium colostrum, yets and herbal extracts, to stimulate immune sistem. Farrowing rate (AI within ≤ 7 days after weaning), in treated sows was significantly ($p < 0.01$) greater (87.6%, 204/233) then in kontrol (untreated) sows (83.7%, 160/205). Average total born and liveborn piglets per litter, in treated (10.4 and 10,3 resp.) and in control sows (10.2 and 10.0 resp.) was not significant different ($p > 0.05$), both the average stillborn piglets per litter was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower in treated (0.14), compared with control sows (0.21). Our data suggest that the application of natural immunomodulators can increase the sows fertility in the intensive pig production.

Key words: diet, supplementation, natural immunomodulators, fertility, sow.

INTRODUCTION

In the intensive pigs production technology, the reproductive sows are confronted by many chronic stressors (Hyun et al., 1998). Stressors significantly reduce the immunity of animals (Potočnjak et al., 2006; Kick et al., 2011), which significantly increases the susceptibility to infectious diseases (Sutherland, 2006). The final result is reduction of sows reproductive performance (Floss and Tubbs, 1999; Stančić et al., 2010).

Classical preventive methods of active and passive immunization or treatment of infectious diseases with antibiotics, have significant negative effects in practical application. Namely, these methods increase the cost of production, and cause extra stress

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in treated animals. In addition, vaccination may have a weaker effect, due to the rapid creation of a new viral strains with different immunogenic properties (Gagrčin et al., 2001; Cromwell, 2002). On the other hand, long-term use of antibiotics creates resistant pathogenic microorganisms, and has a negative impact on human health, due to antibiotic residues in animal products (Pugh, 2002). In the recent period, there are attempts to overcoming these negative effects by supplementing the diet with the natural bioactive substances of plant and animal origin, with the immunogenic properties (immunomodulators) (Zvekić, 2006; Pragathi et al., 2011). However, the recent studies about feeding pigs with natural immunomodulators have shown inconsistent results, related to their effects on the sows reproductive performance in the large productive herds (Gallois et al., 2009).

The aim of this study was to determine whether the treatment by natural immunomodulators, may increase the fertility of sows in the herds of intensive pig production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Investigations were carried out on one pigs farm, with about 1,200 sows, located in the vicinity of the town of Subotica (AP Vojvodina, Serbia). The sows in the reproductive herd were affected with acute PRRS (*Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome*) infection, and in the last two decades, the different forms of PPV (*Porcine Parvo Virus*) infection were detected. These infections had a significant impact on decreasing of sows reproductive performance.

Experimental sows. Total of 476 sows were divided into two groups: 271 treated and 205 untreated (control) sows. Sows in both groups were between 2 and 5 farrowing parity. The first 30 days after artificial insemination (AI), sows are in individual boxes, and then moved to group pens (30 sows in each), up to about 7 days before the scheduled date of farrowing, when it moved to the farrowing facility, with individual pens for sow and litter. Lactation lasts about 35 days. After weaning, sows are moved into group pens (30 sows in each), for estrus detection.

Detection of oestrus and AI. Detection of estrus begins about 24 hours after weaning, by direct contact with sexually mature boar twice daily, at intervals of 10 to 12h. Double AI was performed, 12h and 24h after detection of standing estrus. Insemination was performed by disposable catheters (Foamtip Safe Blue®, Minitübe, Germany). AI dose volume was 100 mL of fresh liquid diluted semen, with 3×10^9 progressively motile sperm. BTS Forte semen extender (Minitübe, Germany) were used. Insemination was performed a few hours after the insemination dose formation.

Experimental treatment. In the period from the fertile insemination to the end of gestation, experimental sows were fed classic diets for pregnant sows, supplemented by 0.3% *Swine Guard SHT* immunomodulator. After farrowing, during lactation, sows were fed conventional diets for lactating sows, supplemented by 0.4% *Guard Swine farrowing* preparations. Between weaning and fertile insemination, sows were fed conventional diets, supplemented with 0.4% *Swine Guard SHT* preparations. Control sows were fed identical classic diets, in certain phases of the reproductive cycle, but not containing immunomodulator preparations.

Immunomodulators preparations. “Hokovit” immunomodulator preparations were used (HU Hofmann AG-CU, 4922 Bützberg, Switzerland). According to the manufacturers declaration, these preparations include: (a) the premium colostrum, whose

role is to support auto-antibodies production, (b) yeast extracts, which regulate the digestive processes and (c) herbal extracts, which act as antioxidants and regulators of normal microflora in digestive tract. *Swine Guard SHT* improves the overall health of the sows immune status, increases milk production and food consumption due to better digestion, reduction of metabolic disorders, increases the number and weight of piglets at farrowing. *Guard swine farrowing* significantly increases the quality and quantity of colostrum and milk production, increases the number and weight of piglets at weaning, reduce the incidence of MMA syndrome, increases the appetite of sows in the season of high ambient temperature and prevent diseases caused by staphylococcal and streptococcal infections.

Analysis of data. Descriptive statistics, t-test, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's test were done in the software package Statistics 10th.

RESULTS

The distribution of estrus reaction, within the first 7 days after weaning is present in Table 1.

Table 1. Estrual reaction after weaning

		Treated sows	Control sows
In estrus within 7 days after weaning	n	233	160
	%	86.0A (233/271)	78.0B (160/205)
Av. interval weaning to estrus, days		5.7A	6.4B

^{A,B} Values with different superscript, within the same rows, are statistically significant different (p<0.01).

Within the first 7 days after weaning, estrus was detected in significantly (p<0.01) greater number (86%) of treated, compared with the control sows (78%). Average weaning-to-estrus interval duration were significantly (p<0.01) shorter in treated (5.7 days) than in the control sows (6.4 days).

Farrowing rate, after AI in the first postlactational estrus is present in Table 2.

Table 2. Farrowing rate

		Treated sows	Control sows
Sows inseminated (AI), n		271	205
Farrowing rate, %	A	87.6 ^{ax} (204/233)	83.7 ^{bx} (134/160)
	B	65.8 ^{ay} (25/38)	64.4 ^{ay} (29/45)
	C	84.5 ^{ax} (229/271)	79.5 ^{bx} (163/205)

A – AI in estrus detected ≤ 7 days after weaning; B – AI in estrus detected ≥ 8 days after weaning;

C – For total sows inseminated.

^{a,b} Values with different superscript, within the same rows, are statistically significant different (p<0.05).

^{x,y} Values with different superscript, within the same columns, are statistically significant different (p<0.05).

The greatest farrowing rate were estimated in the treated sows, that were AI in estrus detected within 7 days after weaning (C = 87.6%), as well as in the all treated sows (C = 84.5%), compared with control sows (A = 83.7%; C = 79.5%). The differences in these values between the treated and control sows were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Significantly lower farrowing rate was achieved in the treated (B = 65.8%) and control sows (B = 64.4%) that were inseminated ≥ 8 days after weaning. However, these differences do not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$).

Average total born, liveborn and stillborn piglets per litter at farrowing is present in Table 3.

Table 3. Litter size at farrowing

	Treated sows	Control sows	Total
Sows farrowed, n	229	163	476
Av. lactation duration, days	34	33	34
Av. total born piglets per litter, n	10.42 ^a	10.23 ^a	10.34
Av. liveborn piglets per litter, n	10.28 ^a	10.02 ^a	10.17
Av. stillborn piglets per litter, n	0.14 ^a	0.21 ^b	0.16

^{a,b} Values with different superscript, within the same rows, are statistically significant different ($p < 0.05$).

The average number of total born (10.42) and liveborn (10.28) piglets per litter in treated sows did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$) in comparison with control sows (10.23 and 10.02, resp.). But the average number of stillborn piglets per litter was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the control (0.21), compared to treated sows (0.14).

DISCUSSION

The various stressogens during pregnancy and lactation, as well as during the period from weaning to fertile insemination, decrease the reproductive performance of sows, by increasing incidence of prolonged weaning-to-estrus interval, rebreedings, abortions and litter size decreasing (Floss and Tubbs, 1999; Potočnjak et al., 2006; Stančić et al., 2010). Reduced immunity increase the susceptibility of animals to infectious diseases (Sutherland, 2006), which are common causes of reproductive disorders (Hogg and Levis, 1997; Gagrčin, 2003; Yeske, 2007; Stančić et al., 2011). Recently, various immunomodulators of plant or animal origin (Zvekić, 2006; Pragathi et al., 2011), or non-specific immunization (Steinmasl and Wolf 1990; Pavičić et al. 2003; Potočnjak et al., 2006), are used in order to increase the immunity of animals subjected to chronic stress in intensive production conditions (Blecha, 2001). Preparations of yeast extract, herbal extract, colostrum, and blood serum is commonly used as a natural immunostimulators (Davis et al., 2004; Gallois et al., 2009; Pragathi et al., 2011; Bonneau and Laarveld, 1999). However, there are not consistent results about effects of natural immunomodulators on sows reproductive performance in the large productive herds (Gallois et al., 2009).

Our results, in a herd with the PRRS and PPV infection presence, show that the addition of natural immunomodulators in the diet can increase the sows reproductive performance. Namely, the number of sows in estrus within 7 days after weaning (86%) and farrowing rate (87.6%) were significantly higher, while average stillborn piglets per litter were lower (0.14) in treated, compared with control, (untreated) sows (78%, 83.7% and 0.21,

resp.). The results of other authors show that infectious diseases significantly reduce sows fertility (Hogg and Levis, 1997; Gagrčin, 2003; Sutherland, 2006; Yeske, 2007; Stančić et al., 2010). In this regard, based on our results, it could be, indirectly, concluded that natural immunomodulators increase the immunity of the treated sows and increase their reproductive performance. However, detailed studies are required to elucidate the physiological mechanisms of natural immunomodulators action and their relations with sows fertility.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results about relations of diets supplementation with natural immunomodulators and sows fertility, it can be concluded:

- 1) Sows treated with natural immunomodulators had a shorter weaning-to-estrus interval, higher farrowing rate and a smaller number of stillborn piglets per litter, compared with control (untreated) sows.
- 2) These findings suggest that the application of natural immunomodulators can increase the sows fertility in the intensive pig production.

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DODAVANJE PRIRODNIH IMUNOMODULATORA U HRANU I FERTILITET KRMAČA

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Izvod

Ispitivan je uticaj ishrane krmača obrocima sa dodatkom prirodnih imunomodulatora, na parametre fertiliteta krmača, na jednoj velikoj farmi svinja u AP Vojvodinini (Srbija). Obrocima suprasnih, laktirajućih i zalučenih krmača, dodati su preparati imunostimulatora, koji su sadržavali biljne ekstrakte, ekstrakte kvasca i kolostruma. Vrednost prašenja, posle VO unutar prvih 7 dana po zalučenju, bila je značajno ($p < 0.01$) veća kod tretiranih (87.6%, 204/233) u odnosu na kontrolne (netretirane) krmače (83.7%, 160/205). Prosečan broj ukupno i živorođene prasadi po leglu tretiranih (10.4 i 10,3) i kontrolnih krmača (10.2 i 10.0), nije bio značajno različit ($p > 0.05$). Međutim, prosečan broj mrtvo rođene prasadi po leglu, bio je značajno manji ($p < 0.05$) kod tretiranih (0.14) u odnosu na kontrolne krmače (0.21). Naši rezultati sugerišu da primena prirodnih imunomodulatora, može povećati fertilitet krmača u intenzivnoj proizvodnji.

Ključne reči: hrana, dodavanje, prirodni imunomodulatori, fertilitet, krmača.

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